

Economic Status and Problems of Women Construction Workers in Palayamkottai Block at Tirunelveli District

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Abstract

In this paper deals the Economic Status and Problems of Women Construction Workers in Palayamkottai Block at Tirunelveli District. The aim of the study is to find out the economic status of women construction workers in Palayamkottai block at Tirunelveli district, to examine the problems faced by women construction workers in Palayamkottai block at Tirunelveli district, to suggest the recommendations for uplift the status of women construction workers. The study based on primary and secondary data. The paper includes problems of women construction workers in Palayamkottai block at Tirunelveli district, government policy measures and suggestion for improvement of the women construction workers in Palayamkottai block at Tirunelveli district. The study concludes that women construction workers status is not fully satisfactory and government should take some proper action to improve their conditions.

Keywords: Construction workers, problems, status, economic conditions and labour, etc.

Introduction

In recent year, women participation in the labour force has risen in many developing countries. Construction sector is important in gross capital formation activity in the country's economy. It is a productive activity as it results in creation of assets. Practically, all the sectors have construction components in them of varying degrees such as 40 per cent in transport and communications, 75 per cent in power, 80 per cent in irrigation and flood control to 100 per cent in housing. Construction work is physically hard and must be carried out in conditions which are difficult and hazardous.

Construction is common importance in all countries. Construction work is physically hard and must be carried out in conditions which are difficult and hazardous. There are serious hazards of accidental injury and even death due to objects or persons fallings from height, collapse of scaffolding caving in of earth work, handling of explosives and soon.

Scope of the Study

The study focused on Economic status and problems of women construction workers in Tirunelveli City. Tamil Nadu is the southernmost State in the Indian sub-continent. It covers a little over 1,30,000 sq.km ., representing about four per cent of India's geographical area. In the State of Tamil Nadu, there are more than 20 lakhs workers engaged in the activity of building construction. construction industry, employs a larger number of workers in the unorganized sector.

Objective of the Study

- To find out the economic status of women construction workers in Tirunelveli city.
- To examine the problems faced by women construction workers in Tirunelveli city.
- To suggest the recommendations for uplift the status of women construction workers.

Methodology

In this study Economic Status and Problems of Women Construction Workers in Tirunelveli City based on Primary and Secondary data. In this study 100 samples are collected. Primary data collected by the respondents through questionnaire method. Secondary method of data collection from various books, journals, newspapers, government publication reports, etc. Tools of analysis Garrett Ranking technique were used for this study.

Review of Literature

Morena et al., (2013) in their paper reveals that it is important to critically analyze the concept and to highlight the distinctive elements of youth mentoring, in the construction industry. The aim of this paper is to look at the experiences, challenges and problems contributing to mentoring of young graduate's construction employees within construction companies. It will indicate whether or not young graduates' construction workers are they being mentored or not, are they involved in any form of mentoring, within their construction companies. This study will examine mentoring of young graduates within organizations, whether they are being mentored or not in the construction industry, as compared to their non-mentored employees; within their companies, it will look at the important characteristics of mentors, potential negative outcomes or problems in mentoring of young graduates and the implications of cultural divide in relation to gender and race, are they being mentored the same or not, this will report more job and career satisfaction, and express lower turnover than their non-mentored counterparts, furthermore it will examine the ways in which mentoring contributes to producing motivated young construction workers within the industry.

Uwakweh, (2015) in his article reveals that increasing construction worker productivity by treating workers as unit of production is flawed because labour is not interchangeable. The human resource approach provides a better framework on how to motivate workers. The conceptual model based on the Expectancy theory of worker motivation is presented with explanation on how it may be used. Research studies available on worker motivation are based on developed countries, thus, this paper explains the research necessary to understand motivating workers in developing countries.

Angel D (2017) has analyzed that the workforce in the unaccounted sector in India was classified as four divisions. They were in terms of occupation, nature of employment, particularly distressed categories and service categories. In adding up to these four divisions, there exist a large section of unorganized labour force such as cobblers, hamals, handicraft artisans, handloom weavers, lady tailors, physically handicapped self employed persons, rickshaw pullers, auto drivers, sericulture workers, carpenters, tannery workers, power loom workers and urban poor.

Result and Discussion

The socio – demographic and economic details are collected from the respondents and problems of domestic workers are given the following tables. Garrett ranking techniques are used for ranking the problems of domestic works in work place.

Table 1 Socio - Demographics of the Respondents

S.No	Factors	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1.	Age	Up to 25 years	20	26
		26-35 years	26	26
		36-45 years	32	32
		Above 46 years	22	22
2.	Religion	Hindu	100	100
		Muslim	0	0
		Christian	0	0
3.	Community	SC/ST	66	66
		BC	10	10
		MBC	24	24
4.	Marital Status	Married	64	64
		Unmarried	06	06
		Widow	22	22
		Divorced	08	08
5.	Education	Illiterate	72	72
		1st to 5th Standard	20	20
		6th to 10th Standard	08	08
6.	Family Type	Joint family	36	36
		Nuclear Family	64	64
7.	Family Size	Less than 3 members	18	18
		3 to 5 members	44	44
		More than 5 members	38	38
8.	Residence Area	Village	68	68
		Town	28	28
		City	04	04
9.	House facility	Own house	62	62
		Rental House	36	36
		Leasing	02	02
10.	Housing type	Pucca	58	58
		Thatched	22	22
		Concrete	20	20

11.	Drinking Water	Own tap	64	64
		Common tap	36	36
12.	Toilet Facility	Own toilet	66	66
		Common toilet	24	24
		Open space	10	10
13.	Drainage facility	Underground drainage system	56	56
		Surface drainage system	18	18
		No drainage system	26	26
14.	Mode of Cooking	Wood	14	14
		Kerosene	72	72
		Gas	14	14

Sources: Primary Data

The above table clearly shows that 32 percent of the respondents are in the age group of 36 – 45 years and 26 percent are from the age group of 25-36 years. This states that the woman in the family had the more responsibility of their family. All the respondents are from Hindu religion. No other religion woman enters into this job in this study area. Majority of the respondents (66 percent) are from the SC/ST category and 24 percent of them are from most backward class community. 64 percent of the respondents are married whereas 11 percent of them are widow and they are running their family with their own income. They did not have any financial support from anybody other than their income. More than two third (72 percent) of the respondents are illiterate while 08 of them are completed their higher secondary school. On regards of the family type, 64 percent of the respondents are on the nuclear family and rest of the respondents was in the joint family. 44 percent of the respondents are had a minimum of 3 member and a maximum of 5 members in their family. 68 percent are living in village.

About the facilities in the respondent's house, 62 percent of the respondents are living in their own house. Among them 58 percent of them are living in the pucca houses where as 22 percent of the respondents are living in the thatched houses. This includes all the respondents who are in their own houses as well as in the rental houses. Of the total respondents, 64 percent of them are having the facility of drinking water in their houses. 66 percent of them are having the toilet facility and 74 percent of them are having the drainage facility in their houses. 72 percent of the respondents are using gas connection as their mode of cooking.

Table 2 Economic details of the Respondents

S.No	Factors	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1.	Salary Time Period	Weekly	06.	06.
		Monthly	94	94
2.	Monthly Income	Rs. 3000 – 6000	24	24
		Rs. 6001 – 9000	74	74
		Rs. 9001 & Above	02	02

3.	Monthly Family Income	Rs. 3000 – 6000	04	04
		Rs. 6001 – 9000	52	52
		Rs. 9001 & Above	44	44
4.	Standard of Living after joining work	Improved	70	70
		Not Improved	30	30
5.	Household Expenditure	Rs. 3000 – 6000	24	24
		Rs. 6001 – 9000	68	68
		Rs. 9001 & Above	08	08
6.	Monthly Saving	No Savings	70	70
		Rs. 1001 – 2000	20	20
		Rs. 2001 – 3000	10	10
7.	Household debt	Rs. 3000 – 6000	30	30
		Rs. 6001 – 9000	20	20
		Rs. 9001 & Above	50	50

Sources: Primary data

Table 2 shows that 94 percent of the respondents are getting their salary in monthly basis. 74 percent of them are earning income between Rs.6001 to 9000 and their family members other than the respondents earn a maximum of up to Rs 9000 per month. 70 percent of the respondents are opined that their economic statuses are improved because of this domestic work. 68 percent of the respondent's family incurred a nominal expenditure of Rs. 6001 to 9000 per month. 35 respondents are says no saving. All the respondents are borrowing money from other sources like employer, co-workers and from money lenders. Of them 50 percent of respondents are borrowing between Rs. 9001 & above per month.

Table 3 Problems of the Respondents

Sl.No	Factors	Weighted average Garret score	Rank
1.	Objection from relatives for going to work	47.71	V
2.	No Fixed Wages	54.07	I
3.	Employment not possible throughout the year	48.35	IV
4.	Lesser wage paid to women than men	50.68	II
5.	No holiday	47.14	VI
6.	Lack of social security	49.21	III

Sources: Primary Data

From the above table shows that, Palayamkottai block in Tirunelveli district, 'No fixed Wage' (54.07%) was found to be the major problem among the construction workers and it was assigned the first rank. It was followed by 'Lesser wage paid to women than men' (50.68%), 'Lack of social security' (49.21%), 'Employment not possible throughout the year' (48.35%), 'Objection from relatives for going to work' (47.71%) and last one 'No holiday' (47.14%) were assigned second, third, fourth, fifth and sixth rank respectively.

Findings of the Study

- More the half of the respondents were above the age of 36. This clearly states that these women have got a vital place in her family.
- All the respondents belong to Hindu religion.
- Two third of the respondents were fell into the SC/ST category.
- Majority of the respondents (64 percent) were married.
- On regards to educational level, most of the respondents (72 percent) were illiterate.
- 64 percent of the respondents were preferring nuclear family than the joint family.
- 44 percent were having the average family size, that is, 3 to 5 members in their family and 38 percent of the respondents were having above average family size, that is, more than 5 members in their family.
- More than two third of the respondents (68 percent) were coming from village to this town for doing domestic work.
- 62 percent of the respondents were residing in their own house and the rest of the respondents were living in rental houses.
- More than half of the respondents, that is, 58 percent of them were living in the pucca house in this study area.
- 64 percent of the respondents were having the drinking water facility, 90 percent of them were having toilet facility and 74 percent of them were having drainage facility in their houses 72 percent of the respondents were using LPG as their mode of cooking.
- 94 percent of the respondents were earning monthly and 74 percent of them were earning between Rs.6001 to 9000 per month.
- 70 percent of the respondents opined that their socio-economic statuses were improved after this domestic work.
- On regards of the household expenditure, 74 percent of them were having a nominal expenditure of rs.6001 to 9000 per month.
- 70 percent of the respondents are says no savings.
- All the respondents were borrowing from various sources and 54 percent of them were borrowing between Rs.9000 & above.
- This study reveals that Palayamkottai block in Tirunelveli district, 'No fixed Wage' (54.07%) was found to be the major problem among the construction workers and it was assigned the first rank. It was followed by 'Lesser wage paid to women than men' (50.68%), 'Lack of social security' (49.21%), 'Employment not possible throughout the year' (48.35%), 'Objection from relatives for going to work' (47.71%) and last one 'No holiday' (47.14%) were assigned second, third, fourth, fifth and sixth rank respectively.

Suggestions

- Fixing wages to keep space with other pain work in unorganized sectors.
- The labour market for construction workers is imperfect and buyer dominated. Therefore, the workers have little bargaining power. The only remedy is to organise them is trade unions. However, many are not aware of the benefits of union. A few who are members of unions have gained noting not even the benefits of welfare schemes, not to speak of fair wages.
- The government has already formulated several welfare schemes for the benefit of manual workers, including construction workers. Results of this study show that the benefits have not reached the need. So, the schemes must be reviewed and operational guidelines be issued.
- Skilled workers are economically well off. Therefore, promotion of skill will help the construction workers. This can be arranged by special training centers for construction workers.

- It is also necessary to give top priority for literacy and family welfare drives, because large families are also seen as a cause of low standard of living, especially among unskilled workers.

Conclusion

The status of construction workers is not fully satisfactory in study area. The government must take necessary steps for construction workers to solve the problems of unemployment and low standard of living. Lack of education and opportunities are the major reasons for their unorganized condition. Therefore they are not able to improve their economic conditions. Implementation of minimum wages will better the status of construction workers. Government should take necessary steps to reduce the inequality of women construction workers. If they are united and organized there is likelihood that their status in the society will be improved.

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